

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NALUMANSI****FIRST NAME: BERNADETTE****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 01****INSTRUCTOR: DR KABIRU GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

ESSENTIALS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

As a first step on the path of my doctoral studies, EUCLID has started me off with essential guidance on academic writing. This is meant to provide an overview of the processes necessary to produce excellent academic writing, necessary for subsequent sharing of evidence-based knowledge that is ably articulated to objectively persuade readers at an international level. In this paper, I present the essentials of academic writing focusing on essay writing basics, use of EUCLID word template, writing style, differences between US and UK English and Latin abbreviations and expressions. My work background over the last 15 years has exposed me to plenty of program-related writing but I always felt a need to improve my academic writing skills to enable, among other things, share research findings. This first period is very exciting as I begin to sense that I am close to my dream.

2) ESSAY WRITING BASICS

An academic essay persuades readers on an idea that is supported by an argument using relevant examples from credible sources (EUCLID ACA-401D Coursepack 2015, 2). It is worth noting that developing an essay is not linearly implemented in one trial. The student needs to have an initial plan on how they will get the final essay ready and to which they dedicate ample time. The student then thinks through their idea, undertakes adequate reading to fully research the idea or topic while noting the key points to guide their writing. The key points are subsequently organized into a second plan of how the essay shall be written which gives rise to a draft essay (EUCLID ACA-401D Coursepack 2015, 3). It is

important that the student reads through the draft more than once and edits and shares the draft with peers or family to read and provide feedback. The key sections of the essay include the introduction, body, and conclusion as well as the references. Interestingly, even a well-written essay is not considered complete until it has been submitted (ACA-401D Coursepack 2015, 5)

3) RULES OF THUMB

Overall, there are general key crosscutting notes to consider in writing academic papers and these include, stating the main thesis or viewpoint, right at the beginning of the paper; keeping a focus on the topic in the little space provided to avoid distracting the reader (EUCLID ACA-401D Coursepack 2015, 43); writing the idea simply and clearly; providing examples to support the idea; communicating seriously out of respect for the audience; ensuring logical flow and avoiding plagiarism (EUCLID ACA-401D Coursepack 2015, 44), a serious offence in all academic writing. These key points provide a checklist to buttress all considerations invested in writing academic papers.

4) RULES OF STYLE

A rule of style details how the student should make citations and references. This is important for readers to easily locate the source of evidence a student uses in academic writing. EUCLID recommends Turabian style which is well explained in the Chicago Manual of Style Crib Sheet (EUCLID ACA-401D Coursepack 2015, 66). It is encouraging to note that the University of Chicago recognized their long-serving staff, Ms. Kate L. Turabian and named this style after her, this points to the benefits of dedicated work for a worthy cause. The Crib Sheet highlights the style and usage of abbreviations, capitalization, quotes, and dates; formatting of pages, titles, text, headings, bibliography, and captions; as well as formatting of footnotes and endnotes.

In the Turabian style, two referencing options are provided, namely, (1) notes and bibliography and (2) in-text (author-date) parenthetical citations and reference lists. It is required for whichever system one uses, to remain consistent throughout the writing. At EUCLID for example, the latter is used in writing EUCLID response papers. The in-text citation and reference require that the student provides the author name, year of publication and page. At the end of the paper, the student then provides an alphabetized reference list.

5) AMERICAN AND BRITISH ENGLISH

EUCLID makes it clear that a student can use either American or British English but not both. I note that I have to pay attention to differences in spellings, meanings and punctuations among others. The guide highlights differences in writing dates and punctuation. It is interesting to note that the University does not restrict students to one type of English over the other. I have the opportunity to continue using British English as

I have in all the decades of my education. It is encouraging to note that the computer will support editing using the language of my preference so I do not have to keep every detail to memory but rather pay attention to the common aspects (EUCLID ACA-401D Coursepack 2015, 54-59).

6) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS

Academic writing requires the use of proper English, as the ACA-401 Course Pack guides:

It is best to create content using "plain language" principles. Plain language (also called plain English) is a writing style that is simple and direct, but not simplistic or patronizing. When writing in plain language, use short sentences with simple words. Avoid jargon, acronyms, and abbreviations. Plain language should be visually inviting, logically organized, and understandable on the first reading (EUCLID ACA-401D Coursepack 2015, 78).

Using Latin is more appropriate in footnotes, reference lists, but not in technical writing. An English equivalent of the Latin abbreviation ought to be used in academic writing hence the guide provides for the abbreviations and expressions in Latin.

7) CONCLUSION

This reading has been somewhat difficult. I had to read the same text more than once to feel that I have understood it. I had assumed that one reading was going to be adequate to take me straight to the response paper. I was specifically motivated by the new learning and the seriousness depicted with all the standards provided which gave me a push to keep returning to the content of this Period. The video, word template, checklists and sample writing in their short straightforward content and delivery have greatly improved my understanding of the text. I am happy that I got introduced to Zotero and Grammarly and have successfully downloaded them. I am convinced that the essentials of academic writing cannot be grasped in one reading season but would require frequent revisiting. The intricacies of what is required in all aspects ranging from punctuation to referencing are likely to get easier with regular practice and use as well as the welcome feedback from the Course Facilitators.

REFERENCES

“ACA-401D Period 1 – EUCLID University LMS.” n.d. Accessed May 30, 2019.

<https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.